

Designing a serious game for participatory urban planning is easier than what it seems: the experience of the Edible City Game

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

1. INDICATORS USED IN THE EDIBLE CITY GAME

The excel files where the indicators are constructed are available at:

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Heat island effect

Higher temperatures are one of the major threats of climate change and urban areas are generally warmer than surrounding rural areas. This so-called “urban heat island” is usually caused by heat absorption in paved material which enlarge heat accumulation during the day. The heat stress indicator is a predefined indicator on Tygron platform. As explained in the platform’s documentation, the heat stress is measured by a barometer of UNESCO-IHE. In the barometer, the heat stress depends on the distribution of heat in relation to the type of land use. Different types of land use are responsible for the warming or cooling effect compared to the ambient temperature. More information can be found on Tygron’s wiki¹.

The heat stress indicator reflects the heat stress average of a neighbourhood. The score is calculated by the next equation:

$$Score = \frac{Max\ target\ value - Average\ heat\ stress}{Max\ target\ value - Target} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

Where, *max target value* is a predefined constant which equals to 1,5. By default, the target is set as -2. The indicator’s score is the average score of all playable neighbourhoods.

Water management

Water storage is key in water management since it helps lowering the flooding and provides an alternative source of water. The water management indicator is calculated using an attribute that represents the water storage capacity of that building in m³/m². Hence, the indicator’s score is the proportion of the total water storage of the city regarding the target.

$$Score = \frac{\sum ws_i * a_i}{1000 * target * s_c} \quad (Eq. 2)$$

¹ [https://support.tygron.com/wiki/Heat_effect_\(Function_Value\)](https://support.tygron.com/wiki/Heat_effect_(Function_Value))

Where w_s is the water storage capacity of the building i (in m^3/m^2); a_i is the surface occupied by the building i ; and s_c is the surface occupied by all buildings (in m^2) of the city c , multiplied by the target (in litres) multiplied to 0.001 to convert to cubic meters. The target is defined by default to 100 l., which is the threshold for a cloudburst (100 litres in 24 hours).

Green accessibility

Greening cities contributes to an increase in wellbeing and enhances the attractiveness of open spaces in cities. At the same time, greening strategies are becoming essential ingredients in urban regeneration (Haase et al., 2017). Within this, ECS can become green areas where people not only stay and use but also engage with (Säumel et al., 2019). This indicator has not been related to public health because several studies found that only access to green spaces, without considering others aspects such as socioeconomic factors, are not related with a health improvement (Tamosiunas et al., 2014; Zuniga-Teran et al., 2019).

The European guidelines for the availability of local public open areas (Tarzia, 2003) defines the minimum distance to a green area as 300 metres for any house. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations extended that by considering only green spaces largen than 0.5 ha. (Nielsen & Bronwen Player, 2009). Accordingly, the indicator measures the proportion of houses that are closer than 300 m. to a green area larger than 0.5 ha, including public parks and ECS.

$$Score = \frac{\text{houses closer than 300 m. to a green area} > 0.5 \text{ ha}}{\frac{Target}{100} * \text{total of houses}} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

By default, the target is set to 100% (all houses must fulfil the condition).

Air quality

Emissions from motor traffic are an important source of air pollution in cities around the world and NO_2 is one of the preminent pollutants emitted and the easiest to measure, thus a good advisor of the total motor traffic pollution (Mayer, 1999). Besides, air quality and NO_2 emissions are also directly related to public health, especially to respiratory diseases but also heart diseases and lung cancer (Kampa & Castanas, 2008). At the same time, vegetation has the ability to remove air pollutants through dry deposition, this contribution can achieve to absorb till 40% of NO_2 emitted by cars (Pugh et al., 2012).

Therefore, this indicator measures how much NO_2 is sequestered by vegetation, including ECS, compared with NO_2 emitted by motor traffic as follows:

$$Score = \frac{Absorbed \text{ NO}_2}{\frac{Target}{100} * Emitted \text{ NO}_2} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The target is the proportion of NO_2 that vegetation should sequester. By default, it is set to 0.4, following the abovementioned study. The emitted NO_2 is calculated by Tygron platform according to traffic flows, for more information see Tygron's wiki². Only vegetation which is in

² [https://previewsupport.tygron.com/wiki/Traffic_NO2_\(Overlay\)](https://previewsupport.tygron.com/wiki/Traffic_NO2_(Overlay))

contact with concentrations higher than 1 µg/m³ are considered to calculate the amount of absorbed NO₂.

Public participation

Community-based ECS foster public participation and share decision-making among all participants, thus empowering the citizens. At the same time, people who participate in ECS are more physically active since most of the work is physical. Therefore, growing your own food is a proved antidote for sloth and obesity (Säumel et al., 2019).

This indicator measures the number of people involved in ECS in each neighbourhood:

$$Score = \frac{People\ involved\ in\ EGI}{\frac{Target}{100} * Inhabitants} \quad (Eq. 5)$$

The indicator's score is the average score of all neighbourhoods. The target is the percentage of people that should be involved in ECS in an optimal scenario.

Green justice

In green infrastructure planning, quite attention has been devoted to environmental justice, which includes elements of distribution, procedure and recognition. In this context, distributional justice relates to the unequal distribution of environmental qualities such as public green spaces (Kabisch & Haase, 2014; Rutt & Gulsrud, 2016). In addition, a more fair distribution of green areas, i.e., closer green areas where they are more needed because of socioeconomic issues, addresses more effectively the urban regeneration and the public health UC, since it is in deprived neighbourhoods where they are more crucial (de Vries et al., 2013).

Hence, this indicator measures the public and private green surface per capita in any neighbourhood and takes the minimum value among all neighbourhoods. The private green surface is considered besides public because, otherwise, neighbourhoods with less surface of private gardens (usually poorer) would be disregarded by the indicator. Hence, the indicator is calculated as follows:

$$Score = \min \left(\frac{\sum green\ surfaces_i}{inhabitants_i} \right) * Target^{-1} \quad (Eq. 6)$$

Where *i* is the neighbourhood. By default, the target is set 9 m²/capita, following the recommendations of the WHO (2010). The indicator's score takes the lowest score among the neighbourhoods.

Green economy

Green infrastructures offer an opportunity for the creation of so-called "Green-Collar jobs", from low-skill, entry level positions to high-skill, higher-paid jobs (Falxa-Raymond et al., 2013). In the context of ECSCS, professional initiatives that are intended to generate some source of income by producing, processing or using food are a proper tool for self-employment as well as for running SMEs with capacity to employ third people (Säumel et al., 2019). Therefore, the indicator measures the number of jobs created by ECS in relation with the work force (inhabitants between 16 and 65) of each neighbourhood:

$$Score_i = \frac{Jobs\ created\ in\ ECS_i}{\frac{Target}{100} * work\ force_i} \quad (Eq. 7)$$

Where i is the neighbourhood. The indicator's score is calculated as the average score of all neighbourhoods. By default, it is set to 3%, in line with proportion of people working in primary sector in western countries.

Food sovereignty

Modern cities almost exclusively rely on the import of resources to meet their daily basic needs, causing several environmental impacts but also social and economic. A study made in Cleveland estimated that Cleveland could produce between 4.2% and 17.7% of the overall consumed food in the city regarding different scenarios, considering fresh produce, eggs, poultry and honey (Grewal & Grewal, 2012). In addition, own-grown food has a direct impact on diet changes, inducing people to consume healthier food, with an obvious impact on public health (Leake et al., 2009; Russo et al., 2017).

Within this context, ECS have an obvious role in cities becoming self-reliant in food since their most direct outcome is the food production. Consequently, this indicator measures the food production (in kg/year) in the city in relation with the overall food demand. The average food consumed by a person in a year is assumed as 300 kg (FAO, 2009).

$$Score_i = \frac{Food\ production_i}{\frac{Target}{100} * 300 * inhabitants_i} \quad (Eq. 8)$$

Where i is the neighbourhood, and the target is the proportion of food sovereignty to achieve (by default, 17%, following the abovementioned study). The indicator's score is calculated as the average score of all neighbourhoods.

Renewable energies

Energy from fossil fuels like carbon and oil is one of the biggest causes of climate change. The transition to renewable energies seems unavoidable and the European Union is doing a great effort on that. In urban environments, the solar energy is the more feasible energy (Redweik et al., 2013). Therefore, this indicator considers the surface occupied by solar panels on roofs compared by the total roof surface of the city.

$$Score = \frac{Solar\ panels\ surface}{\frac{Target}{100} * Roof\ surface} \quad (Eq. 9)$$

Green social housing

The availability of housing is an important challenge for cities. Issues like gentrification and touristification are expelling the most vulnerable neighbours from their homes. Urban greening is also provoking gentrification processes (Rutt & Gulrud, 2016) when it is not accompanied by social housing policies. In this line, this indicator is considering not only the amount of social housing but also if these actions are avoiding this so-called green gentrification:

$$Score = \frac{Floor\ surface\ of\ green\ social\ housing}{\frac{target}{100} * floor\ surface\ of\ housing} \quad (Eq. 10)$$

Where *Green social housing* is social housing closer than 100 m. to a public green area larger than 0.5 ha and social housing represents the buildings of Tygron's category *Affordable housing* or that are owned by any character with this indicator in its assignment. This way the indicator only increases the score when social housing is close to urban green. The total score is the neighbourhoods' average.

In addition to these 10 indicators, players also have a budget indicator to control their finances.

2. CHARACTERS TO PLAY WITH

- **Municipality:** the municipality is represented by the city hall and is the main responsible of the city development. It does not have the ability to construct ECS but it can construct city parks (that can improve some indicators but compete for the space with ECS) and social housing. It has a generous budget. Likewise, it is the responsible for the building permits and the owner of public buildings such as culture centres or sports fields. Budget: 2.000.000€.
- **Neighbours organization:** It represents the organized city neighbours. It is concerned with the liveability of the city. It can create communitarian ECS, but its budget is limited. It is the owner of all houses on behalf of the neighbours. Budget: 100.000€
- **SME organization:** A organization representing the SMEs of the city devoted to urban agriculture. Its actions are aimed to create jobs in the city and making profit. It can create professional ECS and it is the owner of offices and warehouses. Budget: 300.000€
- **Consumers' cooperative:** A group of organized people with the aim to get local healthy food. It is interested in food sovereignty and in upscaling urban farming to the whole city. It can create professional ECS. Budget: 100.000€
- **Social sector:** It represents the economic sector devoted to social issues, such as social workers or businesses that provide employ to vulnerable people. It is pursues social aspects such as fair employment, social cohesion and gentrification. It can create professional ECS and social housing, but their budget is limited. Budget: 200.000€
- **Conservationist NGO:** A group of people who defend the sustainability of . It is aimed to improve all aspects of climate change mitigation and adaptation in the city. It can create communitarian ECS but their budget is limited. Budget: 50.000€
- **Educational sector:** A stakeholder representing teachers and families. Its interests lie on educational activities for students and in urban green areas for recreational purposes. It can create communitarian ECS in the schools' gardens and roofs. Budget: 50.000€.
- **Tourism promotion:** It represents the tourism sector, concerned about the capacity of the city to attract tourism. It does not have the ability to construct ECS but they can construct city parks and it has a large budget. Budget: 3.000.000€

